

MEASURES TO PROTECT THOSE WHO REPORT CORRUPTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6570171>

ANNOTATION

This article describes the ongoing reforms in the prevention of corruption in the country, the adopted legislation, the problems encountered in the prevention of corruption and measures to prevent them, the establishment of a system for reporting corruption crimes, its advantages and disadvantages, corruption. Measures on social protection of the persons who have reported on it, the ways of their financial incentives are stated.

In addition, the main tasks of incentives for individuals who report corruption offenses or otherwise assist in the fight against corruption, a general description of the persons who reported corruption offenses or otherwise assisted in the fight against corruption, the principles on which incentives are based, and given information on the amount of incentives provided to those who reported and assisted in corruption offenses

The experience of some foreign countries in the development of this system was also studied, and suggestions and conclusions were made in this regard.

Key words: corruption, fight against corruption, non-corruption, compliance control, non-corruption sector, person reporting corruption, social protection, economic protection.

I. Introduction

Corruption crimes are an obstacle to the development of any state. For this reason, the ongoing reforms and measures to combat this scourge are being strengthened. Target tasks for their naming are being defined, normative bases are being developed. In particular, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a decree "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026"[1].

The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 (Development Strategy) and the State Program for its implementation in the Year of Human Dignity and Active Neighborhood (State) program) was approved.

The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 sets a number of goals and objectives aimed at improving the fight against corruption. In order to introduce honesty standards in the civil service:

gradual introduction of the system of declaration of income and property of civil servants;

creating effective mechanisms to prevent conflicts of interest in the civil service, ensuring transparency and expanding public participation in the fight against corruption;

In order to identify areas and sectors prone to corruption, increase the effectiveness of the system to eliminate corruption, to form an intolerant attitude to corruption in society:

Introduction of modern information, including artificial intelligence technologies, in the fight against corruption;

establish cooperation with civil society institutions in the fight against corruption, support public oversight;

Strengthening systemic preventive measures in the fight against corruption;

Introduce a system of continuous training of the population and civil servants in the field of anti-corruption;

these include ensuring that regulations are developed on the basis of "non-corrupt legislation".

Apart from a number of reforms have been carried out in recent years, new legislation has been adopted, and changes and additions have been made to existing regulations. As a proof of our opinion, it can be listed that the Law "On Combating Corruption" No. 419, adopted on January 3, 2017, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Procurement" No. 472 adopted on April 9, 2018, adopted on January 8, 2018 Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 457 "On Administrative Procedures", No. 5729 "On measures to further improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 27, 2019, Decree PF-6013 "On additional measures to improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on June 29, 2020, the Cabinet of Ministers of March 2, 2016 Resolution No. 62 "On approval of samples of rules".

Among them is the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of March 2, 2016 No 62 "On approval of the standard code of ethics for employees of public administration and local executive authorities." Also, in accordance with the State Program on Combating Corruption for 2017-2018, adopted to implement the Law on Combating Corruption, the rules of ethics are explained to government officials through trainings, seminars and roundtables. Nevertheless, this type of corruption crime is still high in various areas, including medicine,

education, public service delivery, and in particular licensing and permitting the activities of business entities. This is due to the growth of acquaintances in these areas, the lack of economic and social support of the state (mainly in the field of medicine and education), as well as the lack of regulatory framework for the activities of these areas and the lack of application.

II. Research results and discussion

The above-mentioned regulations set out the issue of improving the measures to be taken in the fight against corruption, one of which is the system of reporting corruption offenses.

This system is more efficient and reliable, ensuring that every citizen is vigilant against corruption. However, this system can endanger the life and personal interests of a person who reported the corruption. For this reason, the reforms implemented in recent years are aimed at addressing this issue. In particular, Article 28 of the Law "On Combating Corruption" No. 419, adopted on January 3, 2017, includes a special article on the protection of whistleblowers, which provides for the protection of whistleblowers. The prosecution of those who report corruption-related offenses is punishable by law [2].

On the basis of these normative documents, the tasks of the system of incentives for those who report corruption are defined, the main tasks of incentives (hereinafter - incentives) are those who report corruption offenses or otherwise assist in the fight against corruption:

formation of an intolerant attitude to all forms of corruption in society and ensuring the effective implementation of state policy in this area;

ensuring early prevention of corruption-related crimes, timely identification and elimination of conditions conducive to this;

to further increase the activity of the population in the fight against corruption and to reward them for their contribution to this area.

Incentives for those who report corruption are based on the principles of legality, fairness, impartiality, transparency, observance of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, as well as ensuring their personal safety and taking into account their wishes.

Individuals who report a corruption offense or otherwise assist in the fight against corruption will be awarded a one-time cash reward if one of the following grounds is met:

a) for the report of an administrative offense related to corruption - in the amount of three times the amount of the basic calculation;

b) the amount of bribe or damage or the value of the appropriated (appropriated) property is up to thirty times the basic calculation amount:

for a crime of low social risk - in the amount of five times the amount of the basic calculation;

for a less serious crime - in the amount of seven times the amount of the basic calculation;

for a felony - in the amount of ten times the amount of the basic calculation;

for a very serious crime - in the amount of fifteen times the amount of the basic calculation;

c) the amount of the bribe or the damage caused or the value of the appropriated (appropriated) property is from thirty to one hundred times the basic calculation amount:

for a crime of low social risk - in the amount of ten times the amount of the basic calculation;

for a less serious crime - in the amount of fifteen times the amount of the basic calculation;

for a felony - in the amount of twenty times the amount of the basic calculation;

for a very serious crime - in the amount of twenty-five times the amount of the basic calculation;

g) if the amount of the bribe or the damage caused or the value of the appropriated (appropriated) property is more than one hundred times the amount of the basic calculation, it is calculated as follows:

for a considerable amount - in the amount of a bribe or damage in the amount of or fifteen percent of the value of the appropriated (appropriated) property;

for a large or very large amount - in the amount of a bribe or damage caused or ten percent of the value of the appropriated (appropriated) property.

In this case, the amount of the bribe or the damage caused or the percentage of the value of the appropriated (appropriated) property shall be based on the minimum amount established by the legislation;

d) five times the amount of the base calculation for reporting the whereabouts of the wanted person, and seven times the amount of the base calculation for simultaneously reporting the whereabouts of two or more wanted persons.

A person shall be rewarded in the form of a thank-you note or a commemorative gift for informing the anti-corruption authorities about the facts important in the investigation and disclosure of corruption crimes or for direct assistance in the investigation of such crimes or operative-search activities.

In addition, the person may also be nominated for a state award in accordance with the legislation for a worthy contribution to the fight against corruption.

The Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall keep records of persons who have reported encouraged corruption offenses or otherwise assisted in the fight against corruption on the basis of information provided by anti-corruption bodies.

In order to ensure the safety of persons, their families and close relatives who have reported corruption offenses or otherwise assisted in the fight against corruption, information about them may be disclosed in accordance with the requirements established by law.

Expenses related to incentives for persons who report corruption offenses or otherwise assist in the fight against corruption shall be covered from the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The norm also provides for strict sanctions against those who falsely report corruption, and the third part does not apply to those who knowingly give false information about corruption offenses, and they are legally liable for disseminating false information[3]. The norm provides for the safety of those who report corruption, but their socio-economic protection remains open.

This measure is reflected in the legislation of developed countries. Article 24.3 of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan “On Combating Corruption” states that a person who reports a crime against corruption or otherwise assists in the fight against corruption is protected by the state and the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan, is encouraged in the manner prescribed by [4].

The Federal Republic of Germany also has this system, which provides socio-economic protection to those who report corruption[5].

This system is being further improved in our legislation as well. In particular, amendments and additions were made to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On Combating Corruption», the Anti-Corruption Agency developed a draft law on amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On Combating Corruption» and posted it on the portal of discussion of draft regulations (The discussion process ended on January 8, 2020)[6].

The draft law provides for a number of amendments and additions to Article 28 of the Law «On Combating Corruption», the content of which is proposed as follows:

The state guarantees the confidentiality of persons who report corruption offenses, as well as the social and legal protection of themselves and their close relatives.

Information on persons reporting corruption offenses is a state secret and cannot be disclosed. Except for the restrictions established by law. Where there is sufficient evidence that those who report corruption offenses, as well as their close relatives, are in fact threatened with violence or destruction of property, the anti-corruption authorities shall protect their lives, health, honor, dignity and take the necessary measures to protect his property.

Assault on persons reporting information on corruption offenses and their close relatives due to the fact that they provided information on corruption offenses shall be punishable by law. Incentives for persons reporting corruption offenses shall be provided in accordance with the procedure established by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This updated norm, in stark contrast to the previous one, provided for social for incentives for persons who reported corruption offenses or otherwise assisted in the fight against corruption. or in the form of a commemorative gift[7].

According to Article 8 of the Charter, the grounds for rewarding a person with a one-time cash reward for reporting a corruption offense or otherwise assisting in the fight against corruption are:

disclosure of such offenses by citizens or stateless persons on the basis of a report to the anti-corruption bodies about a person who demanded a bribe against them or about a corruption offense known to them;

an employee of a non-governmental commercial organization or other nongovernmental organization or state body, state-owned organization or citizens' selfgovernment body shall report to the anti-corruption body (anti-corruption body) and the disclosure of the offense on the basis of a report given by employees directly to their supervisor);

arrest of a wanted person on the basis of a notification to law enforcement agencies about a person wanted for a crime of corruption, except for the fact that law enforcement officers perform such an act in the course of their official duties.

In addition, the Charter stipulates that a person may be nominated for a state award in accordance with the law for a worthy contribution to the fight

against corruption. In this case, the accounts of persons who reported encouraged corruption offenses or otherwise assisted in the fight against corruption shall be maintained and controlled by the Anti-Corruption Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

III. Conclusion

Based on the above, we can say that the protection of the lives of those who report corruption crimes and their close relatives by the state, as well as the widespread use of financial incentives by the state, encourages every citizen in society to be active and fight corruption.

Therefore,

firstly, to further strengthen the system of legal protection of such persons in our country;

secondly, to strengthen the system of criminal law measures to protect the lives and safety of those who report corruption crimes and their close relatives, and to include in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan a probation measure for non-prosecution of persons who report corruption crimes.

In a democratic society, the fight against corrupt organized criminal structures is carried out not only through the application of criminal law measures, but also through the implementation of comprehensive preventive measures aimed at identifying, eliminating, neutralizing and preventing their causes and conditions.

The task is to conduct an in-depth scientific analysis of all the activities of corrupt organized criminal structures and the crimes they commit, the causes of these crimes and the conditions that allow them, a comprehensive, in-depth study of the events, happenings and processes that feed it in all spheres of social life. and requires accurate knowledge.

We also believe that the enrichment of the national anti-corruption system with the experience of foreign countries, as well as its widespread implementation, will help to prevent any interest in public administration.

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